

α -Cleavage during the oxidation of benzazolyl-4-coumarinomethyl sulphides

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2-Mercapto benzazoles (2) have been reacted with various 4-bromomethylcoumarins (1) to obtain diheteroaryl sulphides (3). The attempted oxidation of benzoxazolyl sulphides (3) has resulted in α -cleavage of C-S bond leading to the formation of 4-methyl coumarins (5) and benzoxazolone (6). The benzthiazolyl sulphides (4) were found to be oxidised to corresponding sulphones (4). All the newly synthesised sulphides and sulphones have been screened against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *C. albicans* and *A. niger*.

Aryl sulphides at the allylic position with respect to the biologically important C₃-C₄ double bond in coumarins has resulted in antimicrobials¹ and ligands for silver ion binding². Amongst the various heterocyclic moieties, the 2-benzimidazolyl³ and 4-carbostyryl sulphides⁴ have been reported from our laboratory. The sulphide from 7-methoxy-4-bromomethyl coumarin and 2-thiouracil has been found to exhibit blue fluorescence and is used as label for *t*-RNA⁵. 3,2'-Benzthiazolyl coumarins have been used in photopolymeric compositions and photographic developers⁶. In the light of importance of the hitherto mentioned sulphides and benzthiazolyl coumarins the present paper reports the synthesis of biheterocyclic sulphides, derived from 4-bromomethylcoumarins (1) and 2-mercapto benzthiazole and 2-mercapto benzoxazole (2) and their oxidations.

4-Bromomethylcoumarins (1) are reacted with 2-mercaptobenzazoles (2) in presence of sodium ethoxide in ethanol to give the corresponding sulphides (3). The formation of sulphides is confirmed by their IR spectra, which exhibited the carbonyl-stretching band around 1710 cm⁻¹ and the band around 1610 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the azomethine group. In the PMR spectra (3; X = s, R = 6-CH₃), the methyl protons appeared as singlet at 2.4 ppm, the methylene protons were found to resonate at 4.6 ppm. The coumarin C₃-H and the aromatic protons were found as the singlet 6.7 ppm and multiplet at 7.2-7.6 ppm respectively. The IR and PMR spectral data of sulphides are given in Table 2. These sulphides were further confirmed by their mass spectral data, Table 3.

Attempted oxidation of benzthiazolyl sulphides (X = S)

Table 1. Analytical data of sulphides and sulphones

Compd.	X	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis : Found (Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
3a	S	6-CH ₃	75	210	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₂	63.3 (63.69)	3.5 (3.86)	4.0 (4.12)
b	S	7-CH ₃	70	179	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₂	63.4 (63.69)	3.5 (3.86)	3.9 (4.12)
c	S	5,6-Benzo	70	166	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NS ₂ O ₂	67.0 (67.17)	3.2 (3.48)	3.6 (3.73)
d	S	7,8-Benzo	73	175	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NS ₂ O ₂	67.1 (67.17)	3.3 (3.48)	3.5 (3.73)
e	S	6-OCH ₃	71	143	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₃	60.2 (60.82)	3.5 (3.68)	3.7 (3.94)
f	S	7-OCH ₃	70	160	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₃	60.5 (60.82)	3.6 (3.68)	3.7 (3.94)
g	S	6-Cl	72	213	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ OCl	56.5 (56.74)	2.7 (2.80)	4.3 (4.33)

Table-1 (contd.)

3a	O	6-CH ₃	76	191	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NSO ₃	66.7 (66.85)	4.0 (4.05)	4.2 (4.33)
b	O	7-CH ₃	73	163	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NSO ₃	66.7 (66.85)	3.9 (4.05)	3.7 (3.89)
c	O	5,6-Benzo	75	179	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ NSO ₃	70.0 (70.18)	3.64 (3.5)	3.6 (3.89)
d	O	7,8-Benzo	75	182	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ NSO ₃	70.0 (70.18)	3.64 (3.5)	4.0 (4.12)
e	O	6-OCH ₃	75	163	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NSO ₄	63.7 (63.7)	3.7 (3.86)	3.9 (4.12)
f	O	7-OCH ₃	74	181	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NSO ₄	63.6 (63.6)	3.7 (3.86)	3.9 (4.12)
g	O	6-Cl	70	204	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ NSO ₃ Cl	63.6 (63.7)	2.8 (2.93)	4.0 (4.07)
4a	S	6-CH ₃	70	234	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₄	58.0 (58.2)	3.5 (3.52)	3.5 (3.77)
b	S	7-CH ₃	70	228	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₄	58.1 (58.2)	3.4 (3.52)	3.6 (3.77)
c	S	5,6-Benzo	71	213	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₄	6.19 (61.9)	3.1 (3.21)	3.4 (3.43)
d	S	7,8-Benzo	70	217	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₄	61.8 (61.9)	3.1 (3.21)	3.4 (3.43)
e	S	6-OCH ₃	71	194	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NS ₂ O ₄	55.8 (55.8)	3.2 (3.38)	3.5 (3.61)
f	S	6-Cl	70	235	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ NS ₂ ClO ₄	52.0 (52.1)	2.57 (2.4)	3.5 (3.54)

Table 2. IR and PMR data of sulphides 3 and sulphones 4

Compd.	X	R	IR (cm ⁻¹)		PMR(ppm)			Ar-H 7.12-8.07 (7H, m)
			ν _{C=O}	ν _{C=N}	R	CH ₂ -S	C ₃ -H	
3a	S	6-CH ₃	1715	1605	2.5 (3H, s)	4.75 (2H, s)	6.37 (1H, s)	7.12-8.07 (7H, m)
b	S	7-CH ₃	1721	1618	2.43 (2H, s)	4.7 (2H, s)	6.6 (1H, s)	7.18-8.10 (7H, m)
c	S	5,6-Benzo	1717	1622	-	5.2 (2H, s)	6.54 (1H, s)	7.05-8.40 (10H, m)
d	S	7,8-Benzo	1711	1640	-	4.8 (2H, s)	6.5 (1H, s)	7.3-8.60 (10H, m)
e	S	6-OCH ₃	1715	1610	3.8 (3H, s)	4.8 (2H, s)	6.6 (1H, s)	7.10-8.0 (7H, m)
3a	O	6-CH ₃	1715	1610	2.44 (3H, s)	4.66 (2H, s)	6.7 (1H, s)	7.26-7.60 (7H, m)
b	O	7-CH ₃	1712	1622	2.48 (3H, s)	4.66 (2H, s)	6.66 (1H, s)	7.28-7.69 (7H, m)
c	O	5,6-Benzo	1716	1622	-	5.015 (2H, s)	6.89 (1H, s)	7.28-8.45 (10H, m)
d	O	7,8-Benzo	1727	1612	-	4.76 (2H, s)	6.80 (1H, s)	7.28-8.58 (10H, m)
e	O	6-OCH ₃	1714	1610	3.8 (3H, s)	4.7 (2H, s)	6.70 (1H, s)	7.20-8.0 (7H, m)
4a	S	6-CH ₃	1715	1621	2.4 (3H, s)	5.04 (2H, s)	6.40 (1H, s)	7.0-8.4 (7H, m)

b	S	7-CH ₃	1708	1615	2.50 (3H, s)	5.08 (2H, s)	6.46 (1H, s)	7.28-8.5 (7H, m)
d	S	7,8-Benzo	1720	1634	-	4.97 (2H, s)	6.30 (1H, s)	7.03-8.28 (7H, m)
e	S	6-OCH ₃	1715	1567	3.84 (3H, s)	4.97 (2H, s)	6.40 (1H, s)	7.09-8.27 (7H, m)

by 30% hydrogen peroxide in glacial acetic acid resulted in sulphones (1). The formation of sulphones has been confirmed by their PMR and mass spectra. The sulphone 4; X = S, R = 6-CH₃ showed singlet due to methylene protons at 5.0 ppm. The down field shift is caused by the electron withdrawing sulphone group. The methyl and aromatic protons resonated at expected fields. The mass spectrum (ES) of 4; X = S and R = CH₃ indicated the (M + H) ion as the base peak at *m/z* 372. The PMR and mass spectral data of sulphones (4) are given in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 3. Mass spectral (ES) data of sulphides and sulphones

Compd.	X	R	(M+H) (Base peak)
3b	S	7-CH ₃	340
e	S	6-OCH ₃	356
f	S	6-Cl	359
c	S	5,6-Benzo	376
3b	O	7-CH ₃	324
d	O	7,8-Benzo	360
4a	S	6-CH ₃	372
b	S	7-Me	372

Scheme 1

The products obtained upon the oxidation of benzoxazolyl sulphides 3 (X = O, R = 6-CH₃) did not show any signal in the range of 3–6 ppm, indicating the absence of methylene protons. In turn the PMR spectrum showed the presence of two CH₃ groups, which corresponded to 4,6-dimethyl coumarin. Similarly formation of 4,7-dimethyl coumarin⁷, 6-chloro-4-methyl coumarin, 7,8-benzo-4-methyl coumarin was also confirmed. Literature survey revealed that the alkyl benzoxazolyl sulphides upon oxidation with H₂O₂ in acid medium led to the formation of benzoxazolone⁸ and not sulphones. The 2-benzoxazolyl-benzyl sulphone has been prepared by the vicarious nucleophilic displacement of 2-chloro benzoxazole⁹. A plausible explanation involving α -cleavage has been given in Scheme 2. It is likely that the formed sulphone in the case of benzoxazole, undergoes further cleavage. The C-2 carbon being flanked by the ring oxygen, nitrogen and electron withdrawing sulphone group is highly prone for nucleophilic attack by hydrogen peroxide leading to the formation of 2-benzoxazolone.

Scheme 2

Biological activity :

The antibacterial and antifungal activity of sulphides (3) are screened against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. niger*, *C. albicans*, respectively, by cup plate method^{10,11}. The zones of inhibition were measured in millimeter. The antifungal and antibacterial activities of test compounds were compared with Norfloxacin and gresiofulvin as standards respectively. DMF was used as solvent.

Antibacterial activity :

Nutrient broth was prepared by dissolving peptone (20 g), beef extract (5 g), sodium chloride (5 g), in 1000 ml of boiling distilled water. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 6.2. The media sterilized by autoclaving at 15 lb pressure for 20 min. One day previously of the test the three stock cultures *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, were aseptically inoculated in 5 ml of sterilized nutrient broth and incubated for 16–24 h at 37° in an incubator.

Nutrient agar that served as basal medium was prepared by dissolving peptone (20 g), beef extract (5 g), sodium chloride (5 g), agar (20 g), in 1000 ml-distilled water. The pH of the agar medium was adjusted to 6.8 and sterilized in an autoclave 15 lb pressure for 20 min.

The sterilized media was cooled to about 40° and the inoculation was made with 0.5 ml of substance of required organism. 20 ml of this incubated media was poured into sterile petridishes and then allowed for solidification. The cups or cylinders were made in the petridishes by using a sterile cork borer at equal distances. These cups were filled with 0.1 ml of the sample solution in DMF. These petridishes were placed at room temperature for one hour for proper diffusion, and then incubated at 37° for 24 h in an incubator. The zone of inhibition was measured after 24 h. The results are shown in Table 4.

Antifungal activity :

For antifungal activity, subculture was prepared by

dissolving pancreatic digest of casein (17 g), pancreatic digest of soyabean (3 g), sodium chloride (5 g), dibasic potassium phosphate (2.5 g), and dextrose (2.5 g), in 1000 ml of warm distilled water. The subculture was cooled to room temperature and pH was adjusted to 7.3 using 0.1 N NaOH and sterilized in an autoclave at 121° for 20 min. Two days prior to test, the fungi were inoculated into the medium and incubated at 37° for 48 h.

The casein agar digest medium was prepared by dissolving agar (20 g), pancreatic digest of casein (17 g), pancreatic digest of soyabean medium (3 g), dibasic potassium phosphate (2.5 g) and dextrose (2.5 g), in 1000 ml of distilled water by warming. The pH was adjusted to 7.3 with 0.1 N NaOH and sterilized by autoclaving at 121° for 20 min.

The sterilized agar medium was cooled to 40° and inoculated with fungal cultures. The inoculated media was transferred to sterilized petridishes (about 20 ml) and then allowed to solidify. The cups were made carefully, then 0.1 ml of sample solution or standard was added to the cups. These petridishes were placed at room temperature for one hour for proper diffusion. Then it was incubated at 37° for 48 h, after 48 h the zones of inhibition were measured. The results are given in Table 4.

The benzoxazolyl sulphides are less active compared to benzthiazolyl sulphides. Amongst the benzthiazolyl sulphides maximum zone of inhibition was observed in the

Table 4. Biological activity of sulphides

Compd.	R	X	Antibacterial activity Zone of inhibition in mm			Antifungal activity Zone of inhibition in mm	
			<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. Albican</i>
3a	6-CH ₃	S	10	12	10	16	12
b	7-CH ₃	S	12	11	12	10	12
c	5,6-Benzo	S	18	16	16	18	18
d	7,8-Benzo	S	17	18	18	16	18
e	6-OCH ₃	S	18	12	18	26	24
f	7-OCH ₃	S	22	24	20	18	20
g	6-Cl	S	24	22	16	12	10
3a	6-CH ₃	O	13	10	10	14	12
b	7-CH ₃	O	12	12	11	18	14
c	5,6-Benzo	O	18	16	16	18	18
d	7,8-Benzo	O	16	16	18	16	17
e	6-OCH ₃	O	20	18	22	19	19
	DMF		8	8	8	8	8
	Norfloxacin		25	25	25		
	Greseofluvin					24	24

case of 6-chloro and 7-methoxy derivatives against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*, which were comparable with norfloxacin. The remaining compounds were moderately active against *E. coli* and do not warrant further investigation.

Similar trend was observed in the antifungal activity. The most active compound was 6-methoxy benzothiazolyl sulphides, which inhibit the growth of *A. niger* and *C. albicans* which were comparable with standard Griseofulvin. The other compounds were moderately active.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) were recorded in KBr on Nicolet. Impact-410 FT-IR spectrometer. PMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR using TMS as internal standard.

The general procedures followed for the synthesis of typical compounds are described below.

Preparation of 4-bromoethylacetoacetate :

It is prepared according to Burger and Ulllyot¹².

Preparation of 4-bromomethyl coumarins :

Substituted 4-bromomethyl coumarins were prepared according to Dey and Shankaranarayana¹³.

2-Mercaptobenzoxazole¹⁴ :

2-Mercaptobenzothiazole was a commercial sample and 2-mercaptobenzoxazole was prepared from *o*-amino-phenol according to literature method¹⁴.

Preparation of benzazolyl coumarinomethylsulphides (3) :

Sodium metal (0.12 g) was dissolved in dry ethanol (20 ml) and treated with 2-mercapto benzazole (2) (0.005 mol). To the resulting solution was added 4-bromomethyl coumarin (0.005 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for one hour. The reaction mixture was concentrated and added to the crushed ice. The precipitate separated was filtered and crystallised from a suitable solvent.

Oxidation of benzthiazolyl sulphides (3) to sulphones (4) :

Sulphides (3) were suspended in glacial acetic acid (7 ml) and hydrogen peroxide (30%) (5 ml) was added in portion wise to the cooled suspension. After the completion of addition, the reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and refluxed on water bath for 2 h. Then the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The sepa-

rated solid is filtered and recrystallised from suitable solvent.

Oxidation of benzoxazolylsulphides 3 (X = O) :

Attempted oxidation and similar work up led to the formation substituted 4-methyl coumarins (5) which have been confirmed by their IR and PMR spectra : R = -6CH₃; IR (KBr) 1715 cm^{-1} ; PMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.44 (6H, s), 6.29 (1H, s), 7.23–7.39 (3H, m); R = -7CH₃; IR (KBr) 1720 cm^{-1} ; PMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.41 (3H, s), 2.44 (3H, s), 6.22 (1H, s) 7.1–7.49 (3H, m); R = 7,8-benzo; IR (KBr) 1718 cm^{-1} ; PMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.9 (3H, s), 6.40 (1H, s), 7.28–8.63 (6H, m).

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